

RESIDUAL PERFORMANCE OF ALKALI-ACTIVATED TRM AFTER EXPOSURE TO HIGH TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

Textile reinforced alkali-activated mortars (TRAAM) constitute a new family of composite materials that combines the high mechanical performance of textile reinforced mortars (TRM) with the eco-friendly nature of alkali-activated materials (AAM). Moreover, the utilization of carbon fibers in TRAAM is likely to promote the fire endurance of the developed composite. This study investigates the mechanical performance of carbon-TRAAM specimens after exposure to high temperatures (maximum 600°C). The performance of the TRAAM specimens is compared to the performance of cementitious TRM specimens. The results indicate that carbon-TRAAM are a promising solution for the structural retrofitting and fire resistance upgrade of existing structures.

KEYWORDS

Alkali-activated materials, carbon textiles, fire performance, high temperatures, textile reinforced mortars.

INTRODUCTION

The development of new inorganic-based composite materials that can replace the energy-costly cementitious ones while giving the opportunity to manufacture robust and durable structural elements is of utmost importance to promote sustainable construction. Alkali-activated materials (AAM) are a promising solution toward this target. Studies on AAM have shown promising results about not only their durability and mechanical performance, but also in terms of sustainability, since they can be produced from industrial by-products, i.e., waste materials, such as ferronickel slag (Arce et al., 2022).

The combination of AAM with structural textiles bridges the spearheading technology of textile-reinforced mortars (TRM) with the fast-growing one of AAM and paves the way for strong and eco-friendly inorganic matrix composites. The benefits of the TRM/AAM merging include: (a) non-renewable material savings due to the high specific strength of TRM (high strength with low material volume/weight) and the exploitation of wastes in matrix composition; (b) enhanced durability characteristics owing to both the non-metallic (i.e., noncorroding) nature of the reinforcement and the proven resistance of AAM against various degradation mechanisms, including fire (Arce et al., 2023). Therefore, apart from its superior mechanical performance at ambient conditions, alkali-activated TRM utilizing carbon fibers is likely to conform to fire endurance requirements, too. That is because of the superior performance of carbon fibers at increased temperatures, compared to other common alternatives, such as glass fibers (Tran et al., 2018; Kapsalis et al., 2022).

The scope of this study falls within the development of construction materials compliant with the requirements of sustainability, resilience, adaptability, and livability by introducing a new type of versatile and eco-friendly composite material fit for both new and existing structures, namely textile-reinforced alkali-activated mortars (TRAAM) with carbon fibers. The investigations presented hereby are focused on the mechanical performance of a ferronickel slag (FNS)-based AAM, as well as on the tensile performance of carbon TRAAM specimens with the same FNS matrix. The tests are conducted on specimens that have been exposed only to ambient conditions, as well as on specimens that have previously been exposed to temperatures reaching up to 600°C. The general aim of the study at hand is the utilization of the newly developed composite material into a retrofitting scheme for existing masonry

elements. Hence, the experimental results are compared to results obtained from specimens manufactured with a conventional cementitious mortar used for interventions on masonry elements.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Matrices and reinforcement

Two matrices were used to manufacture the TRM specimens of this study. First, a commercial cementitious mortar with dispersed polymers and short discrete fibers was opted for. This mortar, designated as M1, is an off-the-shelf product that is commonly used for interventions to masonry elements, either for bonding insulation boards or for structural retrofitting by combining the mortar with structural textiles. Therefore, M1 stands as representative of the conventional option. The density of the hardened mortar is equal to 1418 kg/m³.

An alkali-activated mortar utilizing ferronickel slag (FNS) was used as the eco-friendly alternative matrix. FNS was used in two granulometries; a coarse one (with a maximum size of 2 mm) and a ground one (to a d₅₀ of 8.36 μm). The coarse FNS could only be partly activated; hence, it also played the role of the aggregate. The ground FNS functioned as the main precursor. The alkali activation of the slag was achieved via a chemical solution based on potassium silicate and potassium hydroxide. Silica fume was also added to the mixture. The details of the mix design are given in Table 1, and they were based on the mix design found in Arce et al. (2022). The density of the hardened mortar is equal to 2441 kg/m³.

Table 1: Mix design of the FNS mortar

Ingredient	Mass *	Preparation method
Water	7.56	These three ingredients were mixed one day in advance, by simply stirring until the chemical solution was homogenized.
Potassium silicate (KS)	7.23	
Potassium hydroxide (KOH)	1.36	
Coarse FNS sand	48.36	The dry ingredients were mixed together until homogenization. Then the chemical solution was added, and the mixture was mixed for 5 minutes.
Ground FNS sand	33.06	
Silica fume	2.42	
Total	100	

* The presented values are provided in relative proportions

The mechanical properties of the mortars were determined by means of compression and flexure tests on mortar prisms measuring 40×40×160 mm, according to EN 196-1 (CEN, 2016). The mechanical properties of the mortars in ambient conditions were determined 28 days after casting. Additional prisms were manufactured, and 28 days after casting they were exposed to three high temperatures (200°C, 400°C, and 600°C). All heating sessions were carried out within three days and the mechanical tests were performed one day after the last heating session. Hence, the age of the prisms tested after heat exposure was not more than 32 days. All prisms were cured in the same conditions, that is wrapped in plastic foil starting immediately after demoulding until 28 days post-casting.

It is noteworthy that the compressive strength of M1 was found equal to 9.64 MPa while M2 had a strength of 79.70 MPa. It was not feasible to regulate the mix design of M2 such that all performance indicators specially targeting a strengthening intervention could be simultaneously met. This is why - in terms of strength - M2 outperforms M1 when unheated. Therefore, instead of comparing the performance of M2 with a high-strength cementitious mortar (which would not be the realistic choice for the type of application that is investigated in this research, i.e., TRM-based strengthening schemes in normal and post-heated conditions), the comparison of the performance of the mortars will be done in normalized values. Besides, high-strength cement-based mortars show poor post-heating residual strength (Phan, 1996).

The reinforcement of the inorganic matrix composites was an uncoated carbon fiber textile with a weight of 170 g/m^2 (balanced in two orthogonal directions) and a clear mesh size of 10 mm. The density of the carbon fibers is, according to the manufacturer, equal to 1770 kg/m^3 ; thus, the nominal thickness of this textile is equal to 0.048 mm. The tensile strength and modulus of elasticity of the textile were determined by tensile tests on textile strips, and they were found equal to 2231 MPa and 213 GPa, respectively (Kapsalis et al., 2022).

Preparation of the TRM specimens

The TRM specimens were prepared with the same method regardless of the mortar utilized. All specimens were manufactured with a hand layup technique, using metallic moulds. Two layers of the carbon textile were embedded in all specimens, equally spaced through the specimens' thickness. The cross-section of the specimens was equal to $100 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$, and their fiber volume fraction (along the axial direction of the coupons) was equal to 0.96%. The curing of the TRM coupons and their age at testing were identical to the ones of the mortar prisms.

Heating regime

Heating took place in a custom-made furnace. The chamber was constructed with aerated concrete blocks and the heating was provided by two gas burners. The air temperature was measured and controlled in real time with four K-type thermocouples. The same type of sensors was also used to measure the temperature within the specimens. The furnace is shown in Figure 1a. The target air temperatures were 200°C , 400°C and 600°C , for both the mortar prisms and the TRM coupons. The heating rate was approximately equal to $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ until reaching the target temperature (ramp-up); then the temperature was kept constant for a 60-minute long steady-state step, followed by natural cooling down.

Regarding the mortar prisms, three specimens were tested per case (i.e., three M1 prisms and three M2 prisms, for each temperature). One extra specimen for each mortar was manufactured for each target temperature to act as a “dummy” specimen used for the measurement of the temperature inside the prisms. Two thermocouples were embedded in each dummy specimen measuring the temperature at the center of the cross-sections found at 53 mm ($1/3^{\text{rd}}$ of the prism's length) from the edges. The air temperature was measured by four thermocouples fixed a few millimeters above the prisms (Figure 1b).

Regarding the TRM coupons, three specimens were tested per case (i.e., three coupons with M1 matrix and three coupons with M2 matrix, for each temperature). The temperature of the TRM coupons was measured in one specimen of each group by fixing thermocouples into small holes (2 mm diameter, which is 0.5 mm larger than the diameter of the sensors) that were sealed with ceramic wool. The air temperature was measured by four thermocouples that were fixed either a few millimeters above the coupons or in between the coupons. The effect of the position of the sensors is discussed at the section pertinent to the results of the heated specimens. The arrangement of the coupons within the furnace is shown in Figures 1b,c.

Figure 1: Heat treatment furnace and testing apparatus

Mechanical tests

The mortar prisms were tested with the typical apparatus described in EN 196-1 (CEN, 2016), i.e., three-point bending tests on the prisms and then compression of the two fragments. The TRM coupons were tested in tension with a clevis-type apparatus, as described in Donnini and Corinaldesi (2017). Details of the adopted setup are shown in Figure 2 (photos rotated by 90°). The metallic tabs were glued on the specimens with an epoxy-based adhesive. The overall length of the TRM specimens was equal to 600 mm and the anchoring length was 110 mm at each side. The deformation of the free length (380 mm) was measured by two video-extensometers (one on each side of the specimen). The axial strain was calculated based on the deformation measurements.

Figure 2: Tension testing apparatus for the TRM coupons (Kapsalis et al., 2022)

Overview of the experimental campaign

The experimental campaign is summarized in Table 2. In total, 28 mortar prisms and 28 TRM coupons were tested in this study. The test results are presented in the following sections.

Table 2: Overview of the experimental campaign ¹

Mortar prisms		TRM coupons	
Temperature (°C)	Mortar	Temperature (°C)	Matrix
20	M1	20	M1
	M2		M2
200	M1	200	M1
	M2		M2
400	M1	400	M1
	M2		M2
600	M1	600	M1
	M2		M2

¹: the number of specimens in every case was equal to three

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Observations on heated specimens

Mortar prisms

The recorded temperatures during heat exposure of the mortar prisms are shown in Figure 3. The curves corresponding to the air temperature are the average of the four thermocouples used for this purpose. The curves corresponding to the temperature in M1 and M2 are the average of the two sensors that were embedded in each specimen. It is observed that in all tests the temperature of the AAM mortar (M2) was slightly lower than the temperature of the cementitious one (M1) during the heating stages. On the

other hand, during the cooling down stage, the temperature of M2 was higher than M1. This delay in the increase and decrease of the temperature in M2 indicates that M2 has a higher thermal inertia than M1 (as expected, owing to the higher density of M2). The maximum temperature reached at the center of the prisms was practically equal to the maximum (target) air temperature and it was achieved after approximately 70 minutes of exposure.

The heated mortar prisms did not present any visible damage after cooling down. The cementitious mortar (M1) turned from white to grey after heat exposure, which is mainly related to the effect of the fumes from the gas burners. A slight decoloration of the AAM mortar (M2) was observed too, which, apart from the fumes, is also related to the oxidation of the iron phases present in the matrix (Arce et al., 2023). A view of the mortar prisms (after the flexure tests) is given in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Temperature recordings during the heat exposure of the mortar prisms

Figure 4: View of the surface of the mortar prisms with and without exposure to increased temperatures

TRM coupons

The first two heating sessions (exposure to 200°C and 400°C) were performed with the four thermocouples measuring the air temperature fixed a few millimeters above the specimens. It was then observed that hot gas vortices seem to worsen (which directly affects temperature homogenization) as

fire power increases (the temperature increase rate in the coupons is even lower in “test 2 - 400°C” compared to “test 1 - 200°C”). In fact, the temperature of the coupons in the second test could not reach the maximum (target) air temperature of 400°C; the maximum temperature within the coupons was found to be equal to, approximately, 250°C. This was attributed to the poor circulation of the hot air at the lower part of the furnace chamber due to the dense positioning of the coupons. This reasoning led to the assumption that the air in between the coupons was of a much lower temperature than the air a few millimeters above them. This assumption was verified by the third heating session (exposure to 600°C), where the thermocouples monitoring the air temperature were placed in between the coupons instead of above them. It was observed that the required fire power to achieve a temperature condition of 600°C in between the coupons was much larger than in the respective test for the mortar prisms (note that the total volume of the prisms was much lower than that of the coupons, while the spacing among them was less dense; thus, the heated air could circulate easier, and the prisms could be heated more uniformly). In addition, it was observed that when the air in between the coupons had reached 600°C, the temperature within the coupons reached the same value quickly (after 5-10 minutes), which is reasonable owing to the small thickness of the specimens. This way, it was verified that during the first two heating sessions the air in between the specimens was considerably cooler than the target temperatures of 200°C and 400°C. Therefore, the results of the mechanical tests will be given and discussed with reference to the maximum temperatures actually reached in the coupons and not with reference to the nominal maximum (target) temperatures. The above observations on the temperature recordings are shown in Figure 5. It is also observed that the temperature of the M2 coupons increases with a small delay compared to the temperature of the M1 coupons. This agrees with the relevant observation made for the mortar prisms. Finally, as for the mortar prisms, decolorations were observed at the surface of the coupons. In addition, several cracks were observed at the coupons (contrarily to the mortar prisms). The cracks were marked and are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Temperature recordings during the heat exposure of the TRM coupons

It is noteworthy that several coupons presented a small residual curvature (barely visible in photographs) after heat exposure. This could be the result of small eccentricities in the positioning of the carbon fibers inside the coupons, which lead to different elongation/shrinkage among the two sides of the specimens. Similar observations have been reported in Kapsalis et al. (2019). It is also noted that in both cases (M1 and M2) two out of the three coupons exposed to 600°C presented severe cracks and were split in two pieces while being prepared for the tension tests. Thus, only one specimen was mechanically tested in these cases. In fact, the two parts were pulled apart by bare hands causing the effortless rupture of the textile yarns (see Figure 6). This indicates that the carbon fibers were heavily oxidized, a process that affects carbon fibers when they are heated above 400°C and they are in contact with oxygen (Tang, 1996). In addition, the fact that the ruptured fibers could be easily pulled out of the specimens by bare hands indicated that the textile-to-matrix bond was severely deteriorated, too.

Therefore, a profound degradation of the mechanical properties of all TRM coupons exposed to 600°C was expected.

Figure 6: View of the surface of the TRM coupons after heat exposure

Mechanical test results

Mortar prisms

Table 3 shows the maximum temperature that was recorded in each prism (average of two sensors) during each heating session, as well as the respective strength in compression and flexure, for both mortars. Figure 7 shows the evolution of the compressive and flexural strength of both mortars with increasing exposure temperature. The values are normalized for the sake of comparison. It is observed that the cementitious mortar (M1) presents a strength increase in the order of 20-25% after exposure to 200°C (which is not uncommon for cement-based matrices; the presence of polymers play a rather beneficial role here, as well) followed by continuous decay at higher temperatures. After exposure to 400°C, the strength is found less than the original value (in unexposed conditions). Contrarily, the alkali-activated mortar (M2) presents a strength decay (exceeding 25%) after exposure to 200°C, while at higher temperature the strength does not decay significantly any further. A slight (by approximately 8%) further compressive strength degradation is observed at 600°C, while the flexural strength increases significantly after exposure to 600°C, reaching values above the initial (unexposed conditions). The latter is likely related to the phase changing of the minerals included in the mortar and their contribution in sealing micro cracks (Arce et al., 2023). Further studies at micro scale are necessary to fully understand this phenomenon and explain why this is not observed at the compressive strength as well.

Table 3: Compressive and flexural strength of the mortars at normal and increased temperatures *

Temperature (°C)	M1		Temperature (°C)	M2	
	Compression	Flexure		Compression	Flexure
20	9.64 (0.17)	3.20 (0.31)	20	79.70 (2.40)	7.73 (0.64)
199	12.29 (0.48)	3.91 (0.63)	191	48.99 (0.50)	5.82 (0.14)
386	8.68 (0.11)	2.71 (0.16)	404	49.10 (0.65)	5.51 (0.14)
592	6.58 (0.42)	2.66 (0.13)	604	40.90 (6.73)	8.16 (0.35)

* The presented values are averages of three specimens. The standard deviations (σ) are given in the brackets in *Italic fonts*.

Figure 7: Comparative evolution of strength of the mortars with increasing temperature

TRM coupons

Table 4 shows the maximum temperature that was recorded in each coupon (average of two sensors) during each heating session, as well as the respective tensile strength (f_{tu}) and post-cracking tensile modulus (E_f). It is noted that the stresses presented below (thus, the respective elastic moduli as well) are calculated as “textile stresses”, i.e., the applied load is divided by the cross-section of the longitudinal yarns of the embedded textiles (calculated as the nominal thickness of the textile multiplied by the width of the coupons).

Table 4: Tensile strength (f_{tu}) and post-cracking tensile modulus (E_f) of both unheated and heated/cooled TRM coupons *

TRM with M1			TRM with M2		
Temperature (°C)	f_{tu} (MPa)	E_f (GPa)	Temperature (°C)	f_{tu} (MPa)	E_f (GPa)
20	928.6 (60.9)	166.0 (18.4)	20	866.8 (50.8)	147.3 (4.0)
194	940.4 (131.3)	114.4 (11.5)	182	830.1 (141.0)	105.8 (18.0)
239	743.1 (109.6)	114.8 (3.1)	245	817.6 (127.6)	116.0 (9.6)
621	107.3 (-**)	0.0*** (-**)	614	28.9 (-**)	0.0*** (-**)

* The presented values are averages of three specimens, except for the values corresponding to approximately 600°C where the values were obtained from only one specimen. The standard deviations (σ) are given in the brackets in *italic fonts*.

** Only one specimen was tested; thus, the standard deviation cannot be defined.

*** The behaviour was not of a typical tri-linear form; thus, the pre- or post-cracking modulus cannot be determined.

In a graphical representation of the results, Figure 8 shows the stress-strain curves of the tested TRM coupons. In these graphs, the stresses have been calculated as “composite stresses”, i.e., the applied load has been divided by the cross section of the coupons (100 mm × 10 mm). It can be qualitatively observed that the exposure of all coupons (with M1 and M2) at temperatures in the order of 200°C leads to no degradation of strength and a moderate (approximately 30% for both mortars) degradation of the tensile modulus at the post-cracking stage. The strain at failure increases mainly owing to an extension of the multiple cracking stage, as well as the degradation of the tensile post-cracking modulus. The extension of the post-cracking stage was evident also by the denser cracking pattern that the coupons presented after exposure to temperatures of 200°C and higher. The cracking patterns are shown in Figure 9.

a) Coupons with cementitious mortar (M1) b) coupons with alkali-activated mortar (M2)
 Figure 8: Stress-strain response of both unheated and heated/cooled TRM coupons

a) unheated specimens (20°C) b) exposure to approx. 200°C
 c) exposure to approx. 250°C d) exposure to 600°C
 Figure 9: Evolution of the cracking pattern of the TRM coupons with increasing exposure temperature

It is reminded that the temperature of the coupons that were exposed to a nominal air temperature of 400°C did not reach the target value; instead, coupon temperature was limited to approximately 250°C (reasons explained above). Hence, it is noteworthy that exposure to 250°C led to considerable degradation of the mechanical properties, especially at the first and second stage of the stress-strain law (see Figure 8). This comes in contrast to the results obtained for the coupons exposed to 200°C, meaning that a temperature in between 200°C and 250°C seems to be the turning point for the mechanical performance of the coupons, since a rapid decay of their properties initiates. More specifically, it can be seen graphically (see Figure 8) that the cracking stress and corresponding strain are significantly lower than the respective ones at 20°C and 200°C. Since the first stage of the coupons' stress-strain law depends mainly on the properties of the mortar, this observation contradicts the results obtained by the tests on the mortar prisms presented above. It was shown that M1 does not experience any severe degradation of its properties for temperatures up to 400°C, while M2 suffers a steep decay at 200°C but does not decay further for temperatures up to 400°C. These differences may be explained by two different reasons:

- The contribution of the textile reinforcement, in the case of a fiber volume fraction of carbon fibers in the order of 1%, is not insignificant. This is due to the extremely higher strength and elastic modulus of the carbon fibers compared to the mortar. Therefore, the factor $E_f V_f$ is not negligible despite the small V_f and this is due to the very large E_f . Thus, since the contribution of the textile can be considerable even at the first stage, a degradation of the bond between the mortar and the fibers, as well as the thermal deformation mismatch between the matrix and the fibers may lead to decreased properties of the TRM at the first stage, even at temperatures where the mortar and the fibers alone do not show any decay.
- An additional reason is that the properties of the mortar were determined by standard prisms measuring 40×40×160 mm while the TRM coupons had a thickness of only 10 mm. Hence, the small residual curvature of the coupons due to thermal bowing, led to flexural behavior of the coupons at the initiation of the tensile tests. Such residual curvature was not experienced by the thicker mortar prisms, while the direct tensile testing of the coupons is extremely sensitive to such phenomena. Therefore, the aforementioned differences are related to the size effects and the testing method, that differ among the mortar prisms and the TRM coupons.

Another important observation is that the degradation of the multiple-cracking stage of the coupons exposed to 250°C was less severe in the M2 coupons. Even though the alkali-activated mortar presented a higher degradation than the cementitious mortar at temperatures between 200°C and 400°C, the TRM coupons utilizing M2 presented a smoother and shorter multiple-cracking stage (even though the number of cracks was of the same order in both mortars). As a result, the post-cracking stage initiated at a lower strain and higher stress in M2 coupons than in the M1 ones. Consequently, M2 coupons failed at a similar strain as M1 coupons but at a higher stress, indicating a superior performance of the TRAAM over the cementitious counterpart, for temperatures in the order of 250°C. A better, and qualitative visualization of the results is given in Figure 10 that shows the evolution of the strength, the post-cracking tensile modulus, and the strain at maximum stress of the TRM coupons with increasing temperature. It is clear that for a wide range of temperatures the degradation of these properties is relatively lower for the M2 coupons than for the M1 ones. Finally, it is observed that for both mortars, the obtained results are comparable to the ones obtained from previous studies (Kapsalis et al., 2021; Estevan et al., 2022), i.e., they present similar degradation curves as the ones found in the literature, especially regarding the tensile strength where the scatter of the available data from the literature is relatively small.

Figure 10: Evolution of the mechanical properties of the TRM coupons with increasing exposure temperature.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This paper discusses the results of an experimental campaign that tested the residual tensile performance of carbon TRM specimens after exposure to high temperatures (up to 600°C). The main study parameter is the utilization of an alkali-activated mortar (M2), as an eco-friendlier alternative, instead of a conventional cementitious mortar with polymer additives and short dispersed fibers (M1). Despite the superior unheated performance of M2, the TRM coupons presented an equivalent tensile response with both options (M1 and M2) at the same conditions. At increased temperatures, the coupons utilizing M2 experienced (slightly) lower degradation of their mechanical properties for temperatures ranging from 200°C to 450°C. Therefore, the alkali-activated mortar is better suited for TRM applications at such temperatures and significantly better considering the much higher properties at ambient temperatures; thus, it displays a much higher residual capacity in absolute values at increased temperatures. It was also concluded that, even though both mortars showed a promising capacity after exposure to 600°C, when tested as plain mortars, the TRM coupons suffered extremely severe degradation and showed practically zero residual capacity, due to the heavy damage of the textile reinforcement.

Finally, it was concluded that despite the results from the plain mortar tests showing that M1 performs better than M2 at temperatures in the range of 200°C to 400°C, as well as showing that an increase of the mechanical properties was expected at temperatures near 200°C (with the reasonable assumption that carbon fibers do not suffer any degradation at these temperatures), the tests on the TRM coupons did not reflect these results. It is therefore concluded that plain mortar tests are not representative of the results that are expected from the TRM composites. Instead, bond tests should be conducted in the future (either direct textile-to-matrix bond tests or shear bond tests on an appropriate substrate) for a more complete characterization of the composite.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.